

mixture allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The resulting solid product was dried and

TABLE I - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 6*

Compd. no.	R	M.p.**	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	C ₆ H ₅	165 ^a	80	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂
3b	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	193 ^b	71	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂
3c	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	157 ^a	76	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂
3d	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	210 ^a	74	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄
3e	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	198 ^a	71	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ Cl ₂
3f	<i>m</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	232 ^b	73	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ Br ₂
6a	C ₆ H ₅	205 ^b	73	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O
6b	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	159 ^a	75	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂
6c	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	155 ^a	76	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂
6d	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	233 ^a	74	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄
6e	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	211 ^a	76	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ OCl ₂
6f	<i>m</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	236 ^b	71	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ OBr ₂

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**Crystallisation solvent; ^apyridine-water, DMF-water.

crystallised from proper solvent. 4,4'-Di(substituted-tolualdehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)biphenylmethane (3c): ν_{max} 3 300 (NH), 1 510 (C=N) and 1 190 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO) 3.8 (6H, s, CH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, CH₂), 6.9-7.95 (OH, m, 16H Ar + 4NH) and 8.1 (2H, s, CH). 4,4'-Di(substituted-tolualdehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone)biphenyl ether (6c): ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 510 (C=N) and 1 190 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ (DMSO) 3.6 (6H, s, CH₃), 7.15-8.0 (20H, m, 16H Ar + 4NH) and 8.3 (2H, s, CH).

Biological activity: Compounds 2, 4, 3b, 3f, 6c, 6d were tested for antitubercular activity in DMF solvent *in vitro* against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R₀) by serial dilution method. 2 was active at 3.12 μ g ml⁻¹ concentration, 4, 3b, 6c and 6d were found to be active at 25 μ g ml⁻¹ and 3f was found to be active at 50 μ g ml⁻¹ concentration.

Compounds 4, 3d, 6b and 6c were tested for antibacterial activity. None of the compounds tested (MIC in 100 μ g ml⁻¹) was found to have antibacterial activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. P. K. Bhattacharya, Head of Chemistry Department for facilities and encouragement, to Dr. D. E. Fenton of Sheffield University for mass spectra, to Mr. Madhava Rao and Mrs. Sushila Amin for ir and nmr spectra. The authors are thankful to Prof. P. J. Dave, Head of Microbiology Department, M. S. University, Dr. B. J. Khadse, Head of Chemotherapy Department, Haffkine Institute, Bombay for biological screening and to Dr. V. K. Singh for help. One of the authors (D. V.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Synthesis of Novel Analogs of Phthalein Dyes with a Chiral Carbon Atom

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Manuscript received 14 June 1988, revised 16 January 1989,
accepted 21 February 1989

DIFFERENT 2-aryloxybenzoic acids are γ -keto acids of aromatic series and exist in equilibrium as ring-chain tautomers¹. The existence of ring tautomer creates the possibility of condensing it with different phenols to give novel phthalein analogues with a chiral carbon atom. A number of phthalein analogues with a chiral carbon atom have been obtained by condensing 2-benzoyl-3-nitrobenzoic acid with various phenols-aromatic hydroxy compounds.

Results and Discussions

2-Benzoyl-3-nitrobenzoic acid (1) and 2-*p*-toluyl-3-nitrobenzoic acid (2) were prepared with the help of Friedel-Crafts reaction by using nitrophthalic anhydride to react with benzene and toluene respectively in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The acids have been found to exist as a mixture of ring-chain tautomers as evidenced by the spectral data: 1, ν_{max} (KBr) 1 660 (C=O diaryl ketone), 1 695 (C=O), 1 745 (C=O lactonic), 2 650w (OH carboxyl) and 3 500 cm⁻¹ (OH lactol); δ (CHCl₃) 1.85-2.05 (3H, m, nitro-ring protons), 2.3-2.95 (5H, m, ring protons) and 4.25 (1H, s, lactol proton); 2, ν_{max} (KBr) 1 682 (C=O diaryl ketone), 1 710 (C=O), 1 735 (C=O lactonic), 2 600w (OH carboxyl) and 3 100 cm⁻¹ (OH lactol); (CHCl₃) 1.90-2.05 (3H, m, nitro-ring protons), 2.25-2.85 (4H, m, methyl ring proton), 7.55 (3H, s, CH₃) and 4.35 (1H, s, lactol proton).

Different analogs of phthaleins (4a-h and 5a-h) have been prepared (Table 1) by condensing

the acids 1 and 2 with different phenols (3). The condensation with phenols follows the tautomeric equilibrium process which provides the lactols of the acids, and with the excess of 3, the entire acid reacts as lactol.

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF DYES 4 AND 5*

Compd. no.	Reaction condition		M.p °C	Appearance**
	Temp. °C	Time h		
4a	140-50	6	107-09	Dark brown
4b	150-60	2	240-42	Light red
4c	130-40	2	192-95	Dark grey
4d	170-80	3	247-49	Dark brown
4e	180-200	3	300	Brown
4f	160-80	2.5	300	Light brown
4g	130-40	1.5	260-62	Light brown
4h	130	1	240d	Light orange
5a	150-60	6	99-101	Light grey
5b	150-60	2	300	Light red
5c	160-70	2.5	147-49	Dark grey
5d	170-80	2	300	Dark brown
5e	180-200	2.5	300	Light yellow
5f	160-180	2.5	280d	Brown
5g	130-140	3.5	185-87	Light brown
5h	130	1	270	Light pink

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

- 1; R - Phenyl
- 2; R - *p*-Toluyyl
- 4a, 5a; R₁-R₂-R₃-R₄-H; R₅-OH
- 4b, 5b; R₁-R₂-R₃-H; R₄-OH
- 4c, 5c; R₁-R₂-R₃-H; R₄-OH
- 4d, 5d; R₁-R₂-R₃-H; R₄-OH
- 4e, 5e; R₁-R₂-H; R₃-R₄-OH
- 4f, 5f; R₁-R₂-H; R₃-R₄-OH
- 4g, 5g; R₁-R₂-H; R₃-R₄-OOCCH₃
- 4h, 5h; R₁-H; R₂-OH; R₃-R₄-Br

The purity of the dyes (4a to 5h) has been confirmed by paper chromatography. The structures of the dyes (4b and 5b) have been confirmed by chemical and spectral studies. All the dyes showed lactonic C=O ir peaks (1 735-1 785 cm⁻¹) confirming the presence of their lactonic structures.

All the dyes, except 4g and 5g, showed peaks due to phenolic OH (3 300-3 500 cm⁻¹); while in 4g and 5g new peaks at 1 200 and 1 000-1 15 cm⁻¹ (phenolic acetate) appear instead. Potassium hydroxide fusion of the dyes 4b and 5b produced acids 1 and 2 respectively and resorcinol (6). Formation of diacetyl derivatives (4g and 5g) and dibromo derivatives (4h and 5h) further supports the presence of resorcinol moiety in the dyes (4b and 5b). Similarly, the structures of other dyes of the two series have been determined.

The λ_{max} values of these novel analogs of phthalic dyes (4a to 5h; Table 2) have been found comparable to those of the corresponding true phthalic dyes prepared under similar conditions. A number of substituted phthalides^{1,2} and naphthalides have been recently reported. Similarly, synthesis and absorption of a number of phthal-as-eins³⁻⁵ have been achieved and found to be quite comparable to the true phthalic dyes. Our observations are further supported by the above mentioned analogous compounds.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The electronic spectra (ethanol, neutral and alkaline) have been recorded on a Beckmann DU spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer infracord spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a Varian A-60 instrument using TMS as internal reference.

The phenols (phenol, resorcinol, catechol, quinol, phloroglucinol and pyrogallol) were taken in slight excess than the molecular proportions for the acids. Concentrated sulphuric acid (4-6 drops) was used as condensing agent throughout;

TABLE 2 - ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND COLOUR IN DIFFERENT SOLUTIONS OF DYES 4 AND 5

Compd. no.	Colour*			λ_{max} (nm)		
	Neutral	Alkaline EtOH	2% NaOH	Neutral	Alk.	(pH)
4a	Light yellow	Light violet	Light violet	510	530	(9.0)
4b	Dull red	Deep red (GF)	Deep red (GF)	455	500	(9.5)
4c	Brown	Violet	Reddish brown	-	-	-
4d	Brown	Deep brown	Deep brown	-	-	-
4e	Brown	Deep brown	Deep brown	-	490	(8.5)
4f	Light yellow	Reddish brown	Brown	-	-	-
4g	Light yellow	Pink	Pink	-	-	-
4h	Pink	Deep pink (GF)	Deep pink (GF)	520	530	(10.0)
5a	Light yellow	Rose pink	Rose pink	500	540	(9.5)
5b	Red	Deep red (GF)	Deep red (GF)	460	510	(9.5)
5c	Colourless	Brown	Brown	-	-	-
5d	Light brown	Brown	Brown	-	-	-
5e	Light yellow	Yellowish red	Yellowish red	-	500	(8.5)
5f	Light brown	Brown	Light brown	-	-	-
5g	Pale yellow	Reddish (GF)	Deep red	-	-	-
5h	Light pink	Pink (GF)	Deep pink	520	530	(9.0)

*(GF) = Green fluorescence.

Absorption maxima of phthalein analogues of 3-nitrophthalic anhydride: phenolphthalein analogue = 560 (alk. medium); fluorescein analogue = 560 (alk. medium); fluorescein analogue = 480 (neu. medium); 510 (alk. medium); eosine analogue = 530 (neu. medium), 540 nm (alk. medium).

and each dye, when tested, was found free from sulphur.

2-Benzoyl-3-nitrobenzoic acid was prepared by the method reported in literature⁶.

Phenylresorcinolnitrophthal-as-ein (4b; $R_2=R_4=R_5=H$; $R_1=R_3=OH$): A mixture of the acid (1; 5.4 g) and resorcinol (3.0 g) was heated in an oil-bath at 120°. To it concentrated H_2SO_4 (4-6 drops) was added and heated at 150-60° with stirring till the contents became hard-brittle on cooling. The crushed mass was then extracted with 2% aqueous NaOH and the dye stuff was precipitated from the red filtrate by gradual addition of dilute HCl with constant stirring. The solid dye was recrystallised from rectified spirit, dried in an oven (110°) and then in a vacuum desiccator, (4.2 g).

The light red amorphous dye, m.p. 240-42°, gave dull red colour in ethanol, becoming deep red in moderate and strong alkaline media, mol. wt. 370 (Rast) (Calcd. 363) (Found: C, 66.25; H, 3.65; N, 3.90. $C_{20}H_{11}NO_6$ calcd. for: C, 66.13; H, 3.58; N, 3.85%).

Other dyes (Table 1) were prepared similarly (yield 60-70%). The purity of dye (4) was tested on Whatmann no. 1 paper and butan-1-ol and ammonia mixture was allowed to run for 13 h (descending) to give a red spot (single) of the dye.

Acetylation of dye (4): A mixture of the dye (0.5 g), freshly distilled acetic acid anhydride (10 ml) and fused sodium acetate (1.0 g) was refluxed (130-40°) for 3.5 h to give a light yellow solid (0.40 g), m.p. 260-62°, which was found soluble in ethanol, acetone and acetic acid, and was recrystallised from acetone, (0.40 g), m.p. 260-62°, mol. wt. 447 (Found: C, 64.35; H, 3.76; N, 3.20; acetyl, 19.15).

$C_{20}H_{11}NO_6(COCH_3)_2$ calcd. for: C, 64.43; H, 3.80; N, 3.13; acetyl, 19.23%).

Bromination of dye (4b): To the dye (1.0 g) dissolved in minimum quantity of glacial acetic acid, 10% solution of bromine in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was added dropwise with constant shaking. Excess bromine was found to decompose the dyes 4b and 5b into acids 1 and 2 respectively and s-tri-bromoresorcinol (7); hence only a slight excess of bromine in acetic acid than that calculated amount was used. The contents were refluxed (120-25°) for 1 h, then cooled and diluted with minimum quantity of distilled water. The resulting light orange powder (0.85 g) was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 248°d. The dibromo compound dissolved in ethanol imparted pink colour, which on addition of alkali turned to deep pink with green fluorescence, mol. wt. 521 (Found: Br, 30.85. $C_{20}H_{11}NO_6Br_2$ calcd. for: Br, 30.71%).

KOH fusion of dye (4b): A paste of dye (1.0 g) with KOH pellets (8.0 g) was heated on a sand-bath at 300° for 3 h until the colour of dye faded completely. The contents were then dissolved in distilled water (50 ml) and filtered. The excess alkali of the filtrate was neutralised giving a dark brown residue, and the filtrate was further acidified with an excess dilute HCl and left overnight. The resulting white residue (A) was washed well with water and crystallised from benzene/petroleum ether. The filtrate was shaken with ether and evaporation of the excess solvent left a brownish red residue (B).

Residue (A) was identified as the acid 1, confirmed by m.p., m. m.p. and superimposition of its spectra with the authentic sample. Residue (B) was

identified as resorcinol (6) as it responded to ferric chloride, Tollen's reagent and Fehling's solution tests, and further confirmed by m.p. and m.m.p.

The other dyes (4a-h) were prepared and analysed similarly as mentioned in the case of 4b.

2-*p*-Toluy-3-nitrobenzoic acid was prepared⁷ using Friedel-Crafts reaction between toluene and nitrophthalic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. *p*-Toluyresorcinol/nitrophthal-*as*-ein (5b) and other dyes of the series (5a-h) were prepared similarly as dyes 4a-h.

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Studies on Infrared Spectra of some Indenoisocoumarins

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*Manuscript received 9 December 1987, revised 3 March 1989,
accepted 9 March 1989*

INDENO[2,1-*c*]isocoumarins are the derivatives of isocoumarins where the 3,4-position is fused with an indeno ring. The purpose of the present work is to determine the infrared absorption spectra of 5,8-dimethoxyindeno[2' : 3'-3 : 4]isocoumarin, 5,7-dimethoxyindeno[2' : 3'-3 : 4]isocoumarin, 5,7-dimethoxyindeno[2' : 3'-3 : 4]isocoumarin, 7-methoxyindeno[2' : 3'-3 : 4]isocoumarin, 6,7 dimethoxyindeno[2' : 3'-3 : 4]isocoumarin, 5,8,5',6'-tetramethoxyindeno[2' : 3'-3 : 4]isocoumarin, 5,7,5',6'-tetramethoxyindeno[2' : 3'-3 : 4]isocoumarin, 7,5',6'-trimethoxyindeno[2' : 3'-3 : 4]isocoumarin and 6,7,5',6'-tetramethoxyindeno[2' : 3'-3 : 4]isocoumarin have been studied with reference to the frequency of C=O and -O-C= groups of the pyran ring. There was appreciable change due to variation of methoxy group at different positions in benzene ring.

No ir data appear to have been reported for -O-C= group on the compounds studied in the present work.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of the indeno[2,1-*c*]isocoumarins studied shows that these have marked similarity except in some cases. In all the indeno[2,1-*c*]isocoumarins, the ir absorption of C=O of lactone groups is found in the normal range 1 705-1 725 cm⁻¹ except 1b and 1d. 1b and 1d have two values of ir absorption, i.e. 1 700 1 710 and 1 710, 1 700 cm⁻¹. 1e reveals two values of ir absorptions 1 705, 1 720 cm⁻¹ in the normal range 1 705-1 725 cm⁻¹. In all the indenoisocoumarins the ir absorption of -O-C= group is found in the normal range (1 100-1 300 cm⁻¹).

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm⁻¹) DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Molecular formula	M.p.* °C	ν _{C=O}	ν _{-O-C=}
1a	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	161-62 ^a	1 720	1 110
1b	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	145-46 ^b	1 700, 1 710	1 100
1c	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₃	158-59 ^b	1 710	1 108
1d	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	202-05 ^b	1 700, 1 710	1 110
1e	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	123d ^b	1 705, 1 720	1 125
1f	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	160-61 ^c	1 715	1 120
1g	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₄	124-26 ^c	1 708	1 112
1h	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₆	169-71 ^c	1 710	1 115

*Crystallised from : ^aEtOH-EtOAc, ^bEtOH, ^cEtOAc.

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer. The indenoisocoumarins were prepared¹ by the following procedure. Substituted-benzoic acids on treatment with 2-bromoindan-1-one and 2-bromo-5,6-dimethoxyindan-1-one separately in ethanolic NaOH (5%) at pH 6.5 furnished the corresponding 1-oxo-2-indany benzoates, which on cyclodehydration in 90% sulphuric acid² or PPA yielded the respective indeno[2,1-*c*]isocoumarins (1a-h). The compound were purified by repeated fractional crystallisation showing melting point within a range of 1-2°.

- 1a; R¹-OMe; R-R²-R³-R⁴-R⁵-H
- 1b; R-R²-OMe; R¹-R³-R⁴-R⁵-H
- 1c; R¹-R²-OMe; R-R³-R⁴-R⁵-H
- 1d; R¹-R²-OMe; R-R³-R⁴-R⁵-H
- 1e; R¹-R⁴-OMe; R-R²-R³-H
- 1f; R-R²-R⁴-R⁵-OMe; R¹-R³-H
- 1g; R¹-R²-R⁴-R⁵-OMe; R-R³-H
- 1h; R¹-R²-R⁴-R⁵-OMe; R-R³-H